

1 **EXPERIMENTAL METRICS OF THE POWDER LAYER QUALITY IN THE SELECTIVE LASER SINTERING**
2 **PROCESS**

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11

12 **Abstract**

13 According to the literature, the microscopic quality of the powder layer produced in the Selective
14 Laser Sintering (SLS) process is related to the onset of macroscopic defects of the produced powder.
15 This study proposes an experimental procedure able to quantify the quality of the powder layer
16 obtained in the spreading step of the SLS process. A dedicated experimental set-up was developed,
17 able to mimic the powder spreading step of the SLS process and to allow the photographic analysis
18 of its surface. Four commercial polymeric powders for SLS applications have been tested at 2
19 different speeds of the recoater velocity. An image processing analysis converting a series of
20 microscopic images of layer surface in grey level profiles along the spreading direction has been
21 developed. The grey level profiles have been further analysed with a wavelet analysis tool and the
22 major features of the wavelet powder spectral density have been used to calculate specific

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23 indicators of the powder layer quality. The different indicators provide consistent results comparing
24 the tested powders and the testing conditions. The powder ranking according to spreadability
25 indexes, differs from the one obtained using flowability indexes, indicating that spreadability cannot
26 be directly related to flowability.

27 **1 INTRODUCTION**

28 Interest in powder-based additive manufacturing (AM) has been growing fast for several
29 industrial sectors of application [1] producing artefacts made of several materials such as metals,
30 ceramics, polymers, and composites [2]. These techniques allow significant waste minimization for
31 the possibility to reprocess powder excesses and make this production method more sustainable
32 and cheaper than the traditional ones [3] [4]. In Selective Laser Sintering (SLS) objects are produced
33 by the alternating spreading of powder layers and aimed sintering of parts of these layers with the
34 use of a laser source with automated procedures that allow building the geometrical features
35 reported in a CAD drawing [5]. SLS can be relatively inexpensive if compared with other
36 manufacturing processes. However, its main disadvantages are related to the long time
37 requirements for the process [2], especially for large-size objects, poor surface finishing [6] and low
38 mechanical resistance [2]. In particular, these drawbacks can be due to the non-uniform morphology
39 of the powder bed formed during the spreading step [7]. For this reason, in the last years, a large
40 number of studies focused on the relevance of this part of the process.

41 **1.1 Powder flowability in the spreading process**

42 Prescott and Barnum [8] defined powder *flowability* as the propensity to flow in a specific
43 process unit. Therefore, the same powder can behave differently in different process conditions. In
44 SLS, flowability plays a key role because it directly affects the quality of the sintered components.
45 Good spreading conditions are necessary to have tighter powder packing, more homogeneous

46 powder layers and smoother layer surface, which in turn lead to better mechanical and surface
47 properties of the final object [9]. On the contrary, higher porosity or large roughness of the layer
48 could lead to weaker bonds between sintered layers and, consequently, poor mechanical resistance
49 of the artefact [9]. Therefore, it is important to understand whether a powder is suitable to be used
50 in the SLS process by evaluating its capacity to be spread on a plate and underlying powder layers,
51 commonly named spreadability [10]. It is important to highlight that, even if they are related,
52 flowability and spreadability should not be intended as synonyms [11].

53 In the literature, several methods to evaluate the flowability of powders have been reported.
54 However, their relevance to SLS depends on the ability of the flowability characterization to
55 reproduce the proper consolidation conditions of the spreading process.

56 Schmid et al. [12] proposed to use the Hausner ratio, HR, (i.e. the ratio between tap and bulk
57 density) measured by a simplified and rigorous procedure and by round-robin tests of different
58 laboratories to minimise the uncertainty of results. The simplified procedure resulted adequate to
59 characterise and rank different SLS powders according to the authors. However, it can be argued
60 that HR might be not appropriate to evaluate the flowability of powders in SLS, where powder layers
61 form under very low consolidation conditions and without vibrations.

62 Defined consolidation methods like shear testers have been used to characterise the flow
63 properties of SLS polymeric powders at ambient and high temperatures up to the melting point
64 [13,14] utilizing the High Temperature-Annular Shear Cell (HT-ASC) [15]. In these studies, cohesive
65 and frictional properties were characterised at lower consolidation ranges (up to 1 kPa), despite this
66 condition might be not the same during the layer formation [16]. Ruggi et al. [14] found out that the
67 granular Bond (Bo) number was a relevant indicator of the critical powder flowability for effective
68 spreading in SLS machines. Temperature effect was also observed in terms of a poorer flowability
69 for different polyamide powders when approaching the respective melting temperature.

70 Dynamic methods have been also used to characterise powders for SLS. Fereiduni et al. [17]
71 claimed that the interaction between the twisted blade impeller and the powder in a Freeman FT4
72 Powder Rheometer might resemble that of the spreading blade with the powder. In fact, the torque
73 for the rotation of a twisted blade impeller in a fixed bed of particles is measured at low
74 consolidation conditions, even if non-quantitatively specified. The latter measures the resistance to
75 flow of powders when close to a non-consolidated or stress-free condition and hence it is an indirect
76 measurement of the powder flowability. Several characterization studies reported the specific
77 energy to compare the flowability of different powders for SLS [18–20].

78 Rotating drums have been also used to investigate the dynamic flow of SLS powders during
79 spreading [16,21–23]. Amado and his co-workers [21,22] derived from rotating drum experiments
80 (Revolution Powder Analyzer, Mercury Scientific Inc.) different physical parameters: the avalanche
81 angle, the surface fractal and the volume expansion ratio (VER). The first one corresponds to the
82 angle that the powder surface contour forms with a horizontal line in correspondence with the
83 maximum potential energy before the fall of the powder. The surface fractal, which corresponds to
84 the fractal dimension of the free surface of the powder, is an indicator of the rugosity of the powder
85 surface. A low surface fractal means low rugosity and, therefore, a good distribution of the powder.
86 VER is the ratio between the volume occupied by the powder in the drum and the volume after a
87 consolidation procedure by tapping. Therefore, optimal SLS powders should have low avalanche
88 angle, surface fractal and VER. However, by analysing the results, the authors observed that
89 sometimes variations of VER and surface fractal with the material were not consistent. For example,
90 the tested thermoplastic elastomer showed to have a higher surface fractal than a polyamide-based
91 material, but lower VER. Therefore, Amado et al. [21] combined VER and the surface fractal in one
92 parameter to consider both the effects of the Rank Index, that is the ratio between VER and the
93 surface fractal: the higher the index, the better the powder flowability. A similar setup, the

94 GranuDrum rotating drum (Granutools, B) [23], was used to evaluate the powder flowability through
95 the flowing angle (i.e. the dynamic angle of repose) of Ti alloys, at different rotating speeds
96 corresponding to different applied shear rates, as an indicator of the uniformity of powder layers in
97 Selective Laser Melting [24]. Later Amado et al. [22] modified the aluminium rotating drum with a
98 heated core cylinder, to heat the powder to 293 K, to explore typical temperatures of the
99 conventional SLS process, up to values just below the melting point of the material [25]. Above the
100 glass transition temperature of a commercial polyamide 12, better flowability was observed due to
101 a more homogenous packing of the bed of particles.

102 All the aforementioned methods try to assess whether a powder has sufficient flowability
103 for the SLS process or not. However, all of them are indirect and do not necessarily provide
104 exhaustive information on powder spreadability. In fact, during the spreading process, it is likely
105 that powders experience a state of stress which can be different compared to that occurring during
106 the tests with indirect instruments such as a rotating drum or a shear cell. As a result, it is desirable
107 to use a direct method to verify directly the spreadability of powders in conditions as similar as
108 possible to those occurring during the spreading with a tool such as a blade or a roller. Some
109 examples of direct methods are reported in the following section.

110 **1.2 Methods of analysis of the quality of the powder layer**

111 Several recent works have been focused on the experimental assessment of the quality of
112 spread powder layers [7,10,26–29]. A first qualitative visual analysis of the surface quality and the
113 layer density was proposed by Van den Eynde et al. [26].

114 Ahmed et al. [27] produced manually a powder layer with a blade and then “froze” it with
115 an adhesive spray. The quality of the layer surface was analysed using an image analysis tool on SEM
116 images by detecting empty patches as proof of transient jamming [30] of the powder in the heap in

117 front of the moving blade through the gap between the blade and the previous layer. More recently,
118 a step forward was put using a shadowgraphy technique to highlight the surface roughness and the
119 linear defects along the direction of spreading [28]. A promising algorithm based on single-particle
120 detection was recently proposed by Mitterlehner et al. [29].

121 Snow et al. [10] claimed that the spreadability of metal powders was indicated by the
122 fraction of the area of the building plate covered by powder, the rate of powder deposition, and the
123 rate of change of the avalanche angle. These parameters could be somehow correlated with the
124 angle of repose of the powder. A similar concept was recently followed in numerous experimental
125 works, in which it was argued that the spreadability was proportional to the mass of particles within
126 the spread layer [31] or to the packing density in the layer [32,33].

127 A deeper insight into the powder layer structure was provided by in situ x-ray imaging
128 techniques [7,34]. Escano et al. [7] focused on particle-scale dynamics to derive the repose angle,
129 the slope surface speed, the slope surface roughness and the dynamics of powder clusters at the
130 powder front as indicators of powder flow behaviour during spreading. Oropeza et al. [34],
131 reporting spatially resolved powder layer density measurements in a spreading testbed, did not limit
132 to providing average density values but obtained the cumulative distributions which appear a more
133 informative indicator of the uniformity of the particle distribution across the spread layer.

134 A comprehensive comparison between conventional powder flowability testing methods
135 and a spreading test was carried out by Mehrabi et al. [35] on two SLS metal powders. They
136 introduced spreadability expressed as the ratio between the average density of the spread layer and
137 the bulk density of the powder. In particular, the average density of the spread layer was calculated
138 as the ratio of the mass of powder collected in a pocket 1 mm deep engraved on the plate in which
139 the powder spreading experiment was carried out and the pocket volume. The bulk density is

140 intended as the density of the powder in the feeding bed of the SLS apparatus. Such value is well
141 defined in the case of free-flowing powders as the metal powders tested in the study.

142 Sofia [36] developed a simple blade-spreading tool for powder on a plate, as well as a
143 procedure to estimate the layer surface roughness through the analysis of images of a laser blade
144 hitting the layer surface. He found a correlation between surface roughness and the condition
145 approaching the onset of macroscopic irregularity of the layer. This result indicates the study of the
146 surface quality of the powder layer as a tool to quantitatively classify the results of powder
147 spreading experiments. To carry out a reliable powder spreading process and evaluate the quality
148 of the produced layer, a new experimental setup was developed at the University of Salerno. It
149 allows the reproduction of different spreading conditions, such as the shape of the spreading tool,
150 the spreading speed and the gap height below the tool. In this work, this experimental setup was
151 used to test several polymeric powders at different scrolling velocities of the blade. An image
152 analysis procedure, based on the derivation of the time-averaged wavelet power spectrum, is
153 proposed to quantitatively assess the surface quality of experimental powder layers and the results
154 are compared with those of a standard shear testing procedure.

155 **2 EXPERIMENTAL APPARATUSES, PROCEDURES AND MATERIALS**

156 **2.1 Experiments**

157 **2.1.1 Shear test**

158 The powder flowability was measured with an Anton Paar Shear cell mounted on the
159 Modular Compact Rheometer MCR 302 WESP. After filling the bottom ring of the cell with the
160 powder and levelling the powder surface, a full flow function was evaluated by measuring four
161 different yield loci at 1, 2, 4 and 8 kPa pre-shear normal stresses and room temperature. All shear
162 test Experiments were repeated 4 times. The values of the pre-shear normal stresses are lower than

163 usual in shear stress experiments as the adopted values were considered more appropriate for the
 164 powder spreading process in selective laser sintering. The flow function results for the powder can
 165 be seen in **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**. In this Figure, dashed lines report the
 166 limiting flow factors ($ff = \sigma_1/f_c$) separating the classes of the Jenike flowability. The flow factor of
 167 all powders at room temperature is generally in the free-flowing range. Considering the flow factor
 168 at the lowest consolidation stress, even though there was some difficulty in measuring flow
 169 behaviour at low consolidation and some errors are possible, but still, it can be concluded that the
 170 PA6 has better flowability, while TPU, PA6 Black, and PPNAT show a bit of poor flowability compared
 171 to the PA6 at the same consolidation stress.

172

173 **Figure 1 Material flow functions.**

174 **2.1.2 Spreading apparatus**

175 An experimental setup was developed to reproduce the powder spreading process occurring
176 in a typical SLS machine. The main parts of the setup were the spreading system, composed of a
177 blade and a roller recoater, and a deposition plate (Figure 2). The blade could be inclined with
178 respect to the vertical position and experiments can be carried out at different angles of the blade.
179 Different scrolling velocities of the blade could also be adopted. Moreover, the roller recoater could
180 be used as an alternative to the blade at different scrolling and rotational velocities. In principle, the
181 equipment might be also equipped with rollers of different diameters.

182

183 **Figure 2** Different views of the setup used for powder spreading.

184 Three different deposition plates could be used. Each of them presents two square trays of
185 10 cm side each with a fixed depth, of 100, 200 and 300 μm . The aim was to create powder layers
186 with the same thickness as the depth of the trays. The depths of the tray adopted were within the
187 range of layer thicknesses used in the SLS process [37]. The first of the two trays was used to load
188 the powder with a procedure that leaves an excess of powder over the plate level to mimic the

189 powder loading procedure in SLS machines that include the powder lifting process in the powder
190 loading compartment. Therefore, this tray was called “collection tray” (CT). The recoater pushed the
191 powder from the CT towards the “deposition tray” (DT), the second of the two trays of the
192 deposition plate. In particular, as will be explained in more detail in the following, it was possible to
193 adjust the quantity of powder over the DT. In general, the quantity adopted was the one that
194 ensures that the powder spread with the recoater is sufficient to fill the DT including the powder
195 dispersion associated with the recoating process. The precision of the manufacturing of the DT is
196 critical for the significance of the experiments and the tolerances adopted in the manufacturing
197 process were very low and tailored to the minimum depth of the tray, i.e. 100 μm . The spreading
198 plate was thick 10 mm, a value that ensured a large stiffness and that any non-uniformity or
199 unevenness of the powder layer could be attributable only to the quality of the powder spreadability
200 and the other parameters of the spreading process and not o defects of the depth of the deposition
201 tray. The results presented in this work refer only to the blade used as recoater and to the deposition
202 plate of 300 μm depth.

203 A system for the image analysis of the powder layer through a microscope was mounted on
204 the bridge used also for the movement of the spreading apparatus to analyse the powder layer all
205 over its surface. It consisted of a microscope equipped with a digital mechanically connected to the
206 bridge. In particular, two long screws allowed the microscope to be moved in both the vertical
207 direction (z) and the perpendicular direction (y) with respect to the spreading direction (x).
208 Moreover, the microscope could be rotated around the y-axis (Figure 3a) according to the θ_M angle.
209 By using the recoater advancement set up (Figure 3a), it was possible to move the microscope in
210 the x-direction along the position defined by their movement in the y-direction. The focus of the
211 microscope was adjusted by moving the camera in the z-direction. The camera used with the
212 microscope to take photos of the powder layer (Figure 3**Error. L'origine riferimento non è stata**

213 **trovata.**a) was an AmScope MU1603 16 MP, which was connected to a computer via USB 3.0. A led
214 lamp with a 30 W LED with an inclination of 45° (Figure 3b) with respect to the layer was used to
215 illuminate the layer surface.

216
217 **Figure 3 (a) Movements of the microscope and the camera in x, y and z-direction; (b) adequate lighting implemented**
218 **on the powder beds for the image analysis.**

219 **2.2 Procedures**

220 Before using the powders for the experiments, they were dried at 100°C for 1 hour and
221 sieved using a mesh of 250 μm size to retain clusters with dimensions greater than the maximum
222 particle diameter.

223 The procedure adopted in the tests aimed at reproducing as closely as possible the spreading
224 process conditions in a double bed SLS machine in which the feeding bed is raised above the level
225 of the blade edge and the powder sintering bed is lowered of a quantity equal to the thickness of a
226 layer. In an SLS machine, this allows that, with a single movement, the blade recoater takes the
227 material from the feeding bed and, by moving forward towards the sintering bed, generating the
228 new powder layer of the desired thickness. Therefore, in this work, the bed preparation procedure

229 included two parts. The first was, dedicated to generating the powder layer higher than the surface
230 of the plate over the collection tray, simulating the raised feeding bed. The second part was
231 dedicated to the powder transfer from the collection tray to the deposition tray, simulating the
232 generation of a new layer over the sintering bed. The details of how this was achieved are reported
233 in Supplementary Material I.

234 The powder layer was photographed by coupling the optical microscope with a 10×
235 magnification and the camera. The LED lamp was turned to generate a grazing light to highlight
236 unevenness on the surface. Shadows, corresponding to a dark region on the surface images would
237 correspond to the less illuminated side of the surface asperities. The basic idea was that measuring
238 the size of the asperities could indicate the width of the surface roughness.

239 Using the supporting system described above, in which the microscope and the camera were
240 connected to the recoater bridge, it was possible to look at the powder layer at different points in
241 the same conditions of illumination. By keeping also the same distance between the microscope
242 and particles and the magnification in the images, it was possible to directly compare images taken
243 at different points of the same layer and on different powder layers. Furthermore, by combining
244 images taken at adjacent positions along the direction of motion of the bridge, it was possible to
245 reconstruct images of stripes of the layer taken parallel to the recoater advancement direction and
246 at different lateral positions (in the y direction). The details of this procedure are reported in
247 Supplementary Material I.

248 The images were analysed in MATLAB by using its “Wavelet Toolbox” [38]. The aim was to
249 derive the time-averaged wavelet power spectrum for each image and consequently to infer
250 information regarding the quality of the powder, layer. Details of this procedure are given in
251 Supplementary Material I and II.

252 2.3 Materials

253 The five polymeric powders studied in these experiments were chosen between purposely
254 designed for the SLS process. The material properties derived from the technical data sheet and
255 direct characterisation are reported in Table 1.

256 **Table 1 Material properties of PA6 powder: d_{10} , d_{50} and d_{90} are the particle diameters corresponding to the**
257 **10th, 50th and 90th percentile of the cumulative particle size, respectively; $d_{3,2}$ is the Sauter mean diameter, $d_{4,3}$ is**
258 **the the volume mean diameter, ρ_P is the density of the solid; ρ_B is the bulk density of the powder.**

Materials	T_m (°C)	ρ_B (kg/m^3)	ρ_P (kg/m^3)	d_{10} (μm)	d_{50} (μm)	d_{90} (μm)	$d_{3,2}$ (μm)	$d_{4,3}$ (μm)
PA6	210	525	1130	15	46	91	20	50
PA6 LM black	193	590	1370	40	74	129	66	80
PPNAT	140	330	890	35	69	122	36	74
TPU	120-150	500	1100	28	82	163	35	90

259

260 Moreover, to compare the effect of the particle shape and morphology, microscopy
261 analysing was done by Scanning Electron Microscopy. Figure 4 illustrates SEM images all taken at
262 500X magnification.

263 3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

264 3.1 Experimental results

265 Experimental tests were carried out at two values of the scrolling or spreading velocity of
266 the blade (V_S), namely $3 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and $3 \cdot 10^{-2}$ m s⁻¹. Each test was repeated at least 2 times to verify the
267 reproducibility of the results. For each test fresh powder was used, that is powder which had never
268 been used before and which was dried and sieved as already described.

269

270 **Figure 4 SEM images: (a) PA6; (b) PA6Black; (c) PPNAT and (d) TPU.**

271 As a representative of the results obtained with all materials, the macroscopic and
272 microscopic images of the PA6 powder layers are reported in Figure 5. The macroscopic images were
273 obtained by using a 12 MP camera. Visual inspection of macroscopic images reported in Figure 5(a)
274 and (b) does not reveal significant differences in terms of layer surface quality for the two spreading
275 velocities. Instead, in microscopic images reported in Figure 5(c) and (d) some qualitative differences
276 in terms of roughness can be read by inspecting the distribution and the size of brighter and darker
277 areas.

278 As a result, time-averaged wavelet power spectrum analysis was carried out on microscopic
279 images to obtain more quantitative indications related to surface roughness. Figure 6 reports the
280 microscopic images extracted from the powder layers spread at both values of the spreading
281 velocity tested and the corresponding time-averaged wavelet power spectra for the four tested

282 materials. In Supplementary Material III, additional images and their related wavelet power spectra
283 are reported.

284
285 **Figure 5 PA6 powder layer after spreading, macroscopic top view: (a) 3cm/s; (b) 3mm/s and microscopic view: (c) 3**
286 **cm/s; (d) 3 mm/s.**

287 Lengths characterizing the distribution of the powder surface roughness were derived from
288 the time-averaged wavelet power spectra. In particular, due to the shape of the power spectrum
289 function, the analysis was not limited to identifying the peak length, p_l , as the inverse of the
290 wavenumber, corresponding to the maximum value of the power (i.e. the peak value), but it also
291 considered other four length values corresponding to power values equal to the 10% and 60% of
292 the peak value taken both in the lower and in the upper end (i.e. for lengths smaller or larger than
293 p_l), as detailed in Supplementary Material I. In this way, it was possible to obtain five characteristic

294 lengths for each powder and each spreading velocity. Results are shown in the histogram plots
 295 reported in Figure 7, where the black bars correspond to the standard deviation of results obtained
 296 in different tests.

297
 298 **Figure 6 Images of the powder layers and corresponding time-averaged wavelet power spectra obtained for PA6, PA6**
 299 **black, PPNAT and TPU at two spreading velocities (3 cm/s and 3 mm/s).**

300 Inspection of Figure 7 suggests that the surface roughness characteristic lengths are
 301 somehow affected by the scrolling velocity of the blade. In particular, the intermediate lengths
 302 characterizing the distribution (i.e. p_l and lengths at 60% of peak power) generally decrease with
 303 decreasing blade spreading velocity for PA6 and PA6 black powders. As a result, assuming that lower
 304 roughness length values correspond to a more uniformly spread powder surface, a better quality

305 surface layer was obtained for the lower blade scrolling velocity for these powders. Differently, a
 306 much more limited effect of the blade velocity was observed for PNAT and TPU powders.

307
 308 **Figure 7 Values of lengths characterizing the distribution of the powder's surface roughness: (a) PA6; (b) PA6Black;**
 309 **(c) PPNAT and (d) TPU.**

310 The comparison between the characteristic lengths of the surface layer roughness
 311 accounting for the particle size distribution could be of help. Therefore for each powder, Table 2
 312 reports the values of peak length pl divided by the median particle size d_{50} and the ratio between
 313 the range of lengths including spectral values above 60% of the peak value in the distribution, lr_{60} ,

314 and d_{50} . Assuming that increased values of lr_{60} would correspond to less peaked distribution and so
315 indicate better quality ranges, the data of lr_{60}/d_{50} are consistent with those of pl/d_{50} . In fact,
316 comparing results at different velocities worst values of the uniformity of the powder surface at
317 higher speed for the same powder (so at equal d_{50}) are detectable in terms of both lower values of
318 pl and higher value of lr_{60} for PA6, PA6Black and TPU. The opposite appears for PPNAT.

319 Also, ranking the powders according to the quality of the spread powder layer, the so-called
320 “spreadability”, in terms of increasing values of pl/d_{50} and of decreasing values of lr_{60}/d_{50} the
321 ordered sequence should be PA6Black>TPU>PA6>PPNAT with the sequence only slightly changed
322 with an inversion between TPU and PA6 in terms of pl/d_{50} at 3 mm/s. It should be acknowledged,
323 however, that these two powders report very similar results both in terms of pl/d_{50} and lr_{60}/d_{50} ,
324 therefore an inversion, in this case, may also depend on experimental uncertainty.

325 It is remarkable that the “spreadability” ranking just reported does not correspond to the
326 flowability ranking of the powders obtainable by comparing flow factors. Table 2 also reports the
327 values of the material flow factor at the minimum value of the consolidation stress attainable and
328 corresponding to about 1.8 kPa ($ff @ \sigma_{1min}$). In fact, the flowability ranking of the tested powder
329 would in this case be PA6>TPU>PPNAT>PA6Black, remarkably, with a complete change of the
330 ranking position of PA6Black. This discrepancy between powder flowability and powder
331 spreadability has also been reported on metal powders by Mehrabi et al. [35].

332 4 CONCLUSIONS

333 The developed experimental protocol and image analysis procedure allowed a quantitative
334 assessment of the roughness of the layer surface obtained by spreading four different polymeric
335 powders used in the selective laser sintering process. In particular length scales representing the
336 predominant values of the roughness lengths and width of their distribution were identified with
337 the use of a wavelet analysis tool. Lower values of the predominant length, as well as larger values

338 of the prevailing length ranges, have been associated with the quality of the powder layers and if
 339 normalized to the particle size, these parameters provide a consistent metric for powder
 340 spreadability. Accordingly, it was possible to derive a ranking of the powder's spreadability and to
 341 assess the effect of the scrolling velocity of the blade on the quality of the obtained layer surface.
 342 In most cases, but remarkably not always, the quality of the spread layer decreases with decreasing
 343 blade spreading velocity. In agreement with previous studies, the powder flowability ranking
 344 estimated with the powder flow factor may strongly disagree with the powder spreadability ranking
 345 according to the proposed metrics.

346 **Table 2 Ratio between the characteristic lengths of the surface layer roughness and the median particle size d_{50}**

		PA6	PA6Black	PPNAT	TPU
<i>ff</i> @ σ_{1min}		44.7	9.2	11.2	22.1
3 cm/s	<i>pl</i> / d_{50}	6.7	3.5	7.1	5.4
	<i>lr</i> ₆₀ / d_{50}	1.21	1.42	1.00	1.28
3 mm/s	<i>pl</i> / d_{50}	5.0	2.6	7.7	5.2
	<i>lr</i> ₆₀ / d_{50}	1.31	1.66	0.81	1.45

347

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353

354 **NOMENCLATURE**

d_{10}	Particle diameter corresponding to the 10th percentile of the cumulative particle size	[m]
$d_{3,2}$	Sauter mean diameter	[m]
$d_{4,3}$	Volume mean diameter	[m]
d_{50}	Particle diameter corresponding to the 50th percentile of the cumulative particle size	[m]
d_{90}	Particle diameter corresponding to the 90th percentile of the cumulative particle size	[m]
h	Height of image	[px]
l	Width of image	[px]
lr_{60}	Range of lengths including spectral values above 60% of the peak	
L	Lower part of the image representing the portion of the powder layer analysed	
M	Middle part of the image representing the portion of the powder layer analysed	
pl	Peak Length	
U	Upper part of the image representing the portion of the powder layer analysed	
X	Spreading direction	[m]
Y	Perpendicular direction with respect to the spreading direction in the same spreading plane	[m]
Z	Vertical direction	[m]
Greek symbols		
θ_M	Angle of rotation of the microscope around the y axis	[°]
ρ_b	Bulk density of the powder	[kg m ⁻³]
ρ_P	Density of the solid	[kg m ⁻³]
σ_1	Major principal stress	[Pa]
Acronyms		
AM	Additive Manufacturing	
AR	Aspect ratio	

CT	Collection Tray	
CWT	Continuous Wavelet Transform	
DEM	Discrete Element Method	
DRA	Dynamic repose angle	[°]
DT	Deposition tray	
FF	Flow Factor	[-]
HR	Hausner Ratio	[-]
L	Lower part of the image	
M	Middle part of the image	
P	Deposition plate	
PA6	SINTERLINE® POWDER PA6 3400 HT 110 NATURAL	
PA6Black	Ultrasint® PA6 LM BLAK- Low melting Polyamide 6-based powder	
PPNAT	Ultrasint® PP nat 01- Polypropylene-based powder	[-]
PS	Power spectrum	
PSD	Particle Size Distribution	
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy	
SLM	Selective Laser Melting	
SLS	Selective Laser Sintering	
TPU	Ultrasint TPU® 88A- Thermoplastic polyurethane	
U	Upper part of the image	

355

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Supplementary Material I to:

EXPERIMENTAL METRICS OF THE POWDER LAYER QUALITY IN THE SELECTIVE LASER SINTERING PROCESS

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DETAILED SAMPLE PREPARATION PROCEDURE

Powder layer formation

This appendix reports the details of the procedure adopted to simulate in the experimental apparatus the generation of a new powder layer that occurs in a two-moving bed SLS machine

- 1) The edge of the blade was fixed at a certain distance above plate P. Such a distance was set by positioning the steel sheets of a feeler gauge with known thickness in the range 500 - 1000 μm between the tip of the blade and plate P (Figure Error. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-1a).
- 2) After having fixed the blade to its holder and removed the sheets, the powder was poured in front of the blade (Figure Error. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-1b).
- 3) The blade was then moved forward at a scrolling velocity of 3 mm s^{-1} . Since the distance between the CT and DT is just 2 cm, the DT was covered with an aluminium foil to prevent powder from entering into it at this stage.
- 4) Once the CT was completely filled with powder, the blade was moved backwards till it reached a distance of a few centimetres before the CT (Figure Error. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-1c).
- 5) The aluminium foil was removed. The powder, which was deposited outside the borders of the CT, in front and under the blade, was gently removed with a brush (Figure Error. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-1d) and collected on other aluminium foils, located below the plate, to avoid the accumulation of powder in the linear guides, that would have compromised the proper movement of the spreading system. As a result, a powder bed was obtained with length and width equal to those of the CT, namely 10 cm by 10 cm, and a height given by the distance which was fixed between the blade and the plate P in step 1).
- 6) The blade was then lowered on plate P so that no distance remained between the blade edge and the plate, and then moved forward over the deposition tray DT. By doing so, the blade displaced the powder bed from the collection tray to the deposition tray (Figure Error. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-1e).
- 7) Once the blade crossed the whole DT, it was stopped, raised, fixed and moved back up to a few centimetres before the CT. At this point, all the powder outside the DT was removed by using a knife and brushes and collected in aluminium foils, located below the plate P.
- 8) A microscope was located above the powder layer inside the DT for the surface analysis (Figure Error. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-1f).

Specific tests were carried out to define the appropriate amount of powder to cover the CT, by changing the distance between the edge of the blade and the deposition plate P. The distance which guaranteed the total coating of the DT in step 6) turned out to be 880 μm which turned out to be adequate both in case the scrolling velocity of the blade in step 6) was 3 mm s^{-1} and 3 cm s^{-1} .

Figure Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-1 **Main steps adopted for the powder layer formation in the experimental procedure: (a) a gap between the blade and P is guaranteed; (b) the powder is poured in front of the blade after being sieved; (c) the deposition tray is covered with an aluminium foil; (d) the powder outside the collection tray is removed; (e) the blade spreads the powder from the collection tray to the deposition tray; (f) pictures of the powder layer in different points have been taken by using a camera and a microscope.**

Powder layer image analysis

The microscope images were taken following a specific methodology. The surface of the powder layer was ideally divided into a matrix composed of 10 rows and 10 columns, i.e. 100 cells with lengths and widths of 1 cm (Figure I-2). To make a comparison between the photos and forthcoming DEM simulation results, the camera was fixed in correspondence with the fifth row, which is sufficiently far from the walls of the tray. Photos along 1.5 cm of the powder layer were taken for comparison, namely starting from cell number 5 to half of cell number 15 (Figure I-2). 1.5 cm of the powder layer corresponded to 95 pictures. In fact, the microscope, as it was used, was able to focus on the centre of the picture. Therefore, to have the whole portion of the powder layer in focus, many pictures had to be taken. Each picture has a height of 1150 μ m.

I	1	11	21	31	41	51	61	71	81	91
II	2	12	22	32	42	52	62	72	82	92
III	3	13	23	33	43	53	63	73	83	93
IV	4	14	24	34	44	54	64	74	84	94
V	5	15	25	35	45	55	65	75	85	95
VI	6	16	26	36	46	56	66	76	86	96
VII	7	17	27	37	47	57	67	77	87	97
VIII	8	18	28	38	48	58	68	78	88	98
IX	9	19	29	39	49	59	69	79	89	99
X	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100

Figure Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-2 **Ideal representation of the powder layer as a matrix of 10 rows (I to X) and 10 columns to form 100 cells, 1 cm by 1 cm each. The spreading direction corresponds to a movement along different columns, e.g. from 1 to 91. The red hyphenated**

Before taking photos of the powder surface, a calibration procedure was carried out to measure exactly the dimension of the objects detected by the camera. A microscope slide with a graduated scale drawn on it was placed inside the empty collection tray (Figure I-3). In this way, the slide was at the same position as the powder within the deposition tray with respect to the microscope. The distance between two tick marks was 100 μm . Then, the microscope lens was neared to the slide to have a good focus of the scale drawn on the slide and captured by the camera. By using the software of the camera, the distance between the marks was registered for the calibration. Calibration revealed that each picture taken from the camera had a height of 1150 μm and a width of 1650 μm .

Pictures like those reported in Figure I-4 were taken. Since the pictures were not

Figure Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-3 **Calibration procedure based on the measure of the distance between two tick marks on the microscope slide by using the microscope coupled**

Figure Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-4 **Image of the powder layer taken by the camera coupled with the microscope. Some particles are highlighted**

completely in-focus (Figure Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-5a), they were overlapped (Figure Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-5b) to have a clear and continuous representation of the portion of the powder layer, which was captured. For example, pictures of **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**a presented some parts which were not in focus, i.e. the regions in the red hyphenated rectangles. Therefore, these regions were removed by overlapping the pictures and by cutting the remaining parts not in focus (Figure Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-5b). This procedure was followed for all pictures, till a sequence of in-focus images was obtained. The length of the final image obtained by combining single images was approximately $1.5 \cdot 10^{-2}$ m. The final image obtained is like the one reported in Figure Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-7a.

Figure Error. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-5 (a) Regions not in-focus (within the red hyphenated rectangles) are identified and cut off; (b) The images are overlapped to obtain a continuous in-focus picture.

Calculation of the wavelet powder spectrum of the images

The procedure adopted in MATLAB consists of the steps in Figure Error. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-6:

Figure Error. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-6 Image analysing steps.

- 1) The strip of microscopic images is opened in MATLAB;
- 2) It is converted from the RGB to the greyscale image. The resulting image is represented in MATLAB as a matrix of elements. Each element is a pixel with a specific brightness level and it is represented by a 1-byte (8-bit) unsigned integers, representing the local value of the 256 distinct shades of grey between 0, which represents the black colour, and 255, which represents the white colour. The matrix is composed of h rows and l columns, where h is the height of the image

in pixels and l is the width of the image in pixels (Figure Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-7a);

- 3) In each image strip three different one-dimensional grey level traces are obtained along the spreading direction in three different positions of the image along the y -direction (**Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**b): upper (U), middle (M), and lower (L) part of the image. For each position (U, M, and L), strips made of 15 different adjacent rows are taken. Such width corresponds approximately to twice the particle diameter d_{50} . Indeed, it was verified that this height guarantees almost the same signal obtained for larger strips, i.e. greater than twice d_{50} . For each strip a greylevel trace along the x -direction (Figure Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-7b) is obtained as the average value of the pixels belonging to the 15 rows at the same x position. For the U, M and L parts, the rows which were considered are: from the 23rd to the 37th, from the 53rd to the 67th and from the 83rd to the 97th row, respectively.

Figure Errore. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-7 (a) Image of a portion of the powder layer with a height (h) and a width (l) in pixels and its subdivision to obtain local wavelet power spectra; (b) 15 rows for each position (U, M and L) have been considered. For example, for the M position, the rows from the 53rd to the 67th of the matrix (representative of the image) have been extracted to obtain the signal of pixels in the central part of the layer.

- 4) Continuous wavelet transform (CWT) is applied to each of the final three averaged traces to obtain the power spectrum (PS) that is a function of the wavenumber. The default Morse wavelet is used (Morse Wavelets - MATLAB & Simulink - MathWorks Italia);
- 5) Final PS is obtained as the average of the power spectra obtained from the three signals related to the M, U and L portions of the layer;

- 6) The peak of the PS and the range of values of the wavenumber are identified. The range is such that the values of the power in correspondence with the extremes of the range are two-thirds and also 10 per cent of the PS peak value (Figure I-8). By doing so, a range of wavenumbers is identified. Such a range of wavenumbers corresponds to a range of wavelengths, which are assumed to be representative of the characteristic dimension of the powder surface roughness. The objective was to derive useful information about the quality of the powder layer after its distribution with the spreading tool.

Figure Error. Nel documento non esiste testo dello stile specificato.-8
Example of the power spectrum (red line). Other hyphenated lines identify the lower and the upper end of the wavenumber range

Details about the used code are reported in Supplementary Material II file.

Supplementary Material II to:

EXPERIMENTAL METRICS OF THE POWDER LAYER QUALITY IN THE SELECTIVE LASER SINTERING PROCESS

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MATLAB CODE FOR THE CONSTRUCTION OF WAVELET POWER SPECTRA

```
%%%%%
% This matlab m file analyse the image by Wavelet Transform
% to quantify the spread powder bed surface quality
% through the taken micro images
% This file developed by
% Sina Zinatlou Ajabshir and Diego Barletta, December 1, 2020
I=imread('1.jpg'); % The powder layer image is opened in MATLAB
G = rgb2gray(I); % Image is converted to greyscale
h=height(G) % Number of rows of G are counted
w=width(G) % Number of columns of G are counted
defaultValues_h = h1; % The actual height of the image is assigned to the variable "defaultValues_h"
defaultValues_w = I1; % The actual length of the image is assigned to the variable "defaultValues_w"
k1= (defaultValues_h)/(h); % Definition of the first calibration factor k1 i.e. real height of the
image(meter)/image height (pixel)
% Main code for selecting specific rows and strips and for analysing the signals
while(1)
n= input ('insert a number from 1:h'); % User is asked to input the strip location 'n'
m= input ('insert a number for strip thickness'); % User is asked to input the strip width 'm'
% Note that the real strip thickness is equal to (2*m)+1
% A row vector (c) is created. The elements of c are the means of the values of the columns belonging
to the submatrix whose rows are the ones between the position i and j of the matrix G.
b=zeros(1,w);
for i=n-m,j=n+m
c = mean(G([i:j], :), 1);
f=cast(c,'single'); %values in vector c are converted to single-precision
b=b+f; % b is the final signal whose values are the pixel intensities
x = 1:w; % x is the distance range
figure; % figure creates a new figure window using default property values
subplot(3,1,1) % subplot divides the current figure into an 3-by-1 grid and creates axes in the position
1
plot(x,b) Signal is plotted as a function of distance
axis tight % Tight fits the axes box tightly around the data by setting the axis limits equal to the range
of the data.
axis([1 w 0 255]) % axis specifies the limits for the current axes so that the x-axis ranges from 1 to w
and the y-axis ranges from 0 to 255.
title('Signal') % title "Signal" is displayed above the plot
xlabel('Distance (Pixel)') % xlabel labels the x-axis with "Distance (Pixel)"
ylabel('Pixel Values') % ylabel labels the y-axis with "Pixel Values"
yticks([0 100 200]) % yticks sets the y-axis tick values, which are the locations along the y-axis where
the tick marks appear.
[cfs,frq] = cwt(b); % cwt turns the continuous wavelet transform (CWT) of b. Two arrays are created:
cfs which corresponds to the wavelet coefficients and frq which corresponds to the corresponding
frequencies.
```

```

Fs = frq./k1;% Default frequency (1/pixel) is converted to the wavenumber.
%FF = 0:Fs;
%cwt(b)
subplot(3,1,2) % subplot divides the current figure into an 3-by-1 grid and creates axes in position 2.
surface(x,Fs,abs(cfs)) % surface function creates a three-dimensional surface plot, i.e. the scalogram.
The function plots the absolute values of each element in array cfs as heights above a grid in the x-y
plane defined by x and Fs. The colour of the surface varies according to the heights specified by
abs(cfs).
colorbar % colorbar displays a vertical colorbar to the right of the current axes or chart
axis tight
%axis([1 w 1 Fs])
shading flat % The shading function controls the colour shading of surface and patch graphics objects;
flat means that each mesh line segment and face has a constant colour determined by the colour value
at the endpoint of the segment or the corner of the face that has the smallest index or indices.
title('Magnitude Scalogram')
xlabel('Distance (Pixels)')
ylabel('Wavenumber (m^-1)')
%ylim([0 100])
%yticks([0 150 300 450])
fb = cwtfilterbank ('SignalLength',numel(b));
% cwtfilterbank creates a continuous wavelet transform (CWT) filter bank. The default wavelet used
in the filter bank is the analytic Morse(3,60) wavelet, where 3 is the symmetry parameter and 60 is
the time-bandwidth.
[tavgp,centerF]=timeSpectrum(fb,b,'SpectrumType','power','Normalization','pdf');
%[tavgp,centerF]=timeSpectrum(fb,b) returns the time-averaged wavelet power spectrum of the
signal b, using the continuous wavelet transform (CWT) filter bank fb, and the center frequencies. By
default, tavgp is obtained by time-averaging the magnitude-squared scalogram over all times. The
power of the time-averaged wavelet spectrum is normalized to equal the variance of b.
WN=centerF./k1; % center frequencies are converted to wavenumbers.
subplot(3,1,3) % subplot divides the current figure into an 3-by-1 grid and creates axes in position 3.
plot(WN,tavgp) % Plot of the time-averaged wavelet power spectrum of the signal b as function of the
wavenumber is created.
axis tight
%axis([0 Fs 0 1])
title('Power wavelet spectrum ')
ylabel('Power')
xlabel('Wavenumber (m^-1)')
end
m1=input('Do you want to continue, Y/N [Y]:','s') % input(prompt) displays the text in prompt and
waits for the user to input a value
if m1=='N'
break
end
end
end

```

Supplementary Material III to:

EXPERIMENTAL METRICS OF THE POWDER LAYER QUALITY IN THE SELECTIVE LASER SINTERING PROCESS

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DETAILED POWDER SPREADING RESULTS

Material: PA6

Figure III-1 PA6 powder layer after spreading, macroscopic top view: (a) 3cm/s; (b) 3mm/s

PA6
3 cm/s

Figure III-2 PA6 powder layer spread at 3cm/s: a) 4 independent microscopic views; b) corresponding wavelet power spectra.

PA6
3 mm/s

Figure III-3 PA6 powder layer spread at 3mm/s: a) 4 independent microscopic views; b) corresponding wavelet power spectra.

Material: PA6 Black

3 cm/s

3 mm/s

(a)

(b)

Figure III-4 PA6 Black powder layer after spreading, macroscopic top view: (a) 3cm/s; (b) 3mm/s

PA6Black
3 cm/s

(a)

(b)

Figure III-5 PA6 Black powder layer spread at 3cm/s: a) 2 independent microscopic views; b) corresponding wavelet power spectra.

PA6Black
3 mm/s

(a)

(b)

Figure III-6 PA6 Black powder layer spread at 3mm/s: a) 2 independent microscopic views; b) corresponding wavelet power spectra.

Material: PPNAT

Figure III-7 PPNAT powder layer after spreading, macroscopic top view: (a) 3cm/s; (b) 3mm/s

PPNAT
3 cm/s

(a)

(b)

Figure III-8 PPNAT powder layer spread at 3cm/s: a) 3 independent microscopic views; b) corresponding wavelet power spectra.

PPNAT
3 mm/s

(a)

(b)

Figure III-9 PPNAT powder layer spread at 3mm/s: a) 2 independent microscopic views; b) corresponding wavelet power spectra.

Material: TPU

Figure III-10 TPU powder layer after spreading, macroscopic top view: (a) 3cm/s; (b) 3mm/s

Figure III-11 TPU powder layer spread at 3cm/s: a) 3 independent microscopic views; b) corresponding wavelet power spectra.

TPU
3 mm/s

(a)

(b)

Figure III-12 TPU powder layer spread at 3mm/s: a) 2 independent microscopic views; b) corresponding wavelet power spectra.